

Pyrimido-Thiazolo-Thiadiazines

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Some Pyrimido (2,1-*b*) thiazolo (4,5-*e*) (1,3,4) thiadiazines have been synthesised by the condensation of 1-amino-2-mercapto-4,4,6-trialkyl-1*H*, 4*H*-pyrimidines with 5-bromo-*N*-aryl-rhodanines.

THE great utility of thiazoles¹⁻⁹ has aroused considerable interest in the possible synthesis of new potential compounds in which the thiazole ring is fused with another biologically active nucleus. With a view to achieve such a system, the synthesis of pyrimido (2,1-*b*)-thiazolo (4,5-*e*) (1,3,4)-thiadiazines has been undertaken. The choice of the fusion of pyrimidine and thiadiazine rings with the thiazole ring is based on the fact that these ring systems have largely been seized upon to prepare a large number of therapeutically important compounds¹⁰⁻¹³

The synthesis of this hitherto unknown ring system has been achieved by first preparing *N*-aryl rhodanines (I)¹⁴. The *N*-aryl rhodanines have been converted into 5-bromo *N*-aryl rhodanines (II) by treating with bromine in glacial acetic acid. The 5-bromo *N*-aryl rhodanines upon condensation with various 1-amino-2-mercapto-4,4,6-trialkyl-1*H*,4*H*-pyrimidines (III)

The first step would be formation of the intermediate IV which could cyclise in two ways to give rise to V or VI. However, in the present case, the intermediate IV could not be isolated as is evident by the absence of I.R. absorption peak in 1680-1640 cm⁻¹ region, characteristic of tertiary amides, in the isolated products.

Out of structure V and VI, structure V finds support from analytical results and by the absence of N-H peak in the I.R. region at 3500-3200 cm⁻¹.

Close scrutiny reveals that II and III could react in another way also to give rise to VII, through the formation of IVa but again the possibility of VII is ruled out on the basis of absence of N-H band in the 3500-3200 cm⁻¹ region (Scheme II)

Experimental

N-aryl-rhodanines (I) : These were prepared according to the method of Braun¹⁴. The yields, solvent for crystallisation, m.p. and analytical data of these compounds is tabulated in Table 1

5-Bromo-*N*-phenyl rhodanine (II; Ar = C₆H₅)
Bromine (5.7 g; 1.8 ml) dissolved in glacial acetic acid was added slowly to a solution of *N*-phenyl-rhodanine (7.5 g) in 150 ml of the same solvent at 40°-50°. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature overnight, diluted with ice cold water, the product collected by filtration, washed with sodium carbonate solution followed by water and crystallised

Other phenyl substituted 5-bromo-rhodanines were prepared in a similar way. The data regarding these 5-bromo-*N*-phenyl rhodanines is tabulated in Table 2

Synthesis of 6,8,8-trimethyl-3-phenyl-4*H*,8*H*-pyrimido (2,1-*b*) thiazolo (4,5-*e*) (1,3,4) thiadiazine 2(3*H*)-thione (V; R = CH₃, Ar = C₆H₅) : 1 Amino-2-mercapto-4,4,6-trimethyl-1*H*,4*H*-pyrimidine (0.89 g, 0.01 mol) and 5-bromo-*N*-phenyl rhodanine (1.5 g, 0.01 mol) dissolved separately in ethyl acetate (25 ml each) were mixed at 40° and refluxed on a steam bath for 6 hr. After cooling, the product was collected under suction and the filtrate concentrated when a further quantity of the product was obtained. Both the solids were crystallised separately and were found

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

yielded the pyrimido (2,1-*b*)-thiazolo (4,5-*e*) (1,3,4)-thiadiazines (V). (Scheme 1).

TABLE 1—N-ARYL RHODANINES (I)

S.No.	Ar	Yield %	m.p. °C	Molecular formula	Analytical results	
					Found%	Required%
1.	C ₆ H ₅ -	57	192	C ₉ H ₇ NOS ₂	N, 6.38	6.70
2.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ -	62	160	C ₁₀ H ₉ NOS ₂	N, 6.21	6.28
3.	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ -	51	147	C ₁₀ H ₉ NOS ₂	N, 6.03	6.28
4.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄ -	61	165	C ₁₀ H ₉ NO ₂ S ₂	N, 5.90	5.86
5.	<i>p</i> -C ₂ H ₅ OC ₆ H ₄ -	56	188	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ NO ₂ S ₂	N, 5.49	5.53
6.	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ -	50	127	C ₉ H ₆ ClNOS ₂	N, 5.83	5.75

All these compounds were crystallised from glacial acetic acid.

TABLE 2—5-BROMO-N-ARYL RHODANINES (II)

S.No.	Ar	Yield %	m.p. °C	Molecular formula	Analytical results	
					Found%	Required%
1.	C ₆ H ₅ -	85	153	C ₉ H ₈ BrNOS ₂	N, 5.16	4.86
2.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ -	75	202	C ₁₀ H ₈ BrNOS ₂	N, 5.01	4.63
3.	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ -	66	176	C ₁₀ H ₈ BrNOS ₂	N, 4.96	4.63
4.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄ -	68	165	C ₁₀ H ₈ BrNO ₂ S ₂	N, 4.42	4.40
5.	<i>p</i> -C ₂ H ₅ OC ₆ H ₄ -	65	200	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ BrNO ₂ S ₂	N, 4.35	4.22
6.	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ -	62	206	C ₉ H ₅ BrClNOS ₂	N, 4.34	4.34

All these compounds were crystallised from ethanol.

TABLE 3—PYRIMIDO (2,1-*b*) THIAZOLO (4,5-*e*) (1,3,4) THIA DIAZINES (V)

S.No.	Ar	R	Yield %	m.p. °C	Molecular formula	Analytical results	
						Found%	Required%
1.	C ₆ H ₅ -	CH ₃	72	170	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ BrN ₄ S ₃	N, 12.29	12.69
2.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	68	174	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ BrN ₄ S ₃	C, 44.37 H, 4.38 N, 11.98	44.84 4.18 12.31
3.	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	60	202	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ BrClN ₄ S ₃	N, 11.64	11.77
4.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	61	205	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ BrN ₄ OS ₃	N, 11.53	11.88
5.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ -	C ₂ H ₅	50	320	C ₁₈ H ₂₁ BrN ₄ S ₃	N, 12.42	11.94
6.	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ -	C ₂ H ₅	59	298	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ BrClN ₄ S ₃	N, 11.89	11.44
7.	<i>p</i> -C ₂ H ₅ OC ₆ H ₄ -	CH ₃	61	241	C ₁₈ H ₂₁ BrN ₄ OS ₃	N, 11.05	11.55

Compounds 1 to 4 and 7 were crystallised from glacial acetic acid and 5 and 6 from ethanol.

to be identical as established by same m.p., m.m.p., and R_f values.

Various 1-Amino 2-mercapto-4,4,6-trialkyl-1*H*,4*H*-pyrimidines were condensed with various 5-bromo

N-aryl rhodanines in a similar way. The data, regarding the solvent for crystallisation, yield, m.p. and analytical results is tabulated in Table 3.

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